

THE ROLE OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION ON COGNITIVE DECLINE OF ELDERLY PATIENTS WITH ALZHEIMER'S AND VASCULAR COGNITIVE IMPAIRMENT

*Valkova M.
MD, PhD*

University Hospital "Sofamed", Sofia, Bulgaria

Abstract

Arterial hypertension (AH) and cognitive impairments frequently coexist among elderly. The aim of our study was to examine the association between AH and cognitive decline among elderly patients with Alzheimer's disease (AD), Vascular cognitive impairment (VCI) and mixed (AD and VCI) cognitive impairment (MD).

Material and methods: We examined 100 patients with AH (on average age of 76.72 ± 7.59 years, 28 males and 72 females, 24 with AD, 38 with VCI and 38 with MD) and 46 patients without AH (on average age of 76.67 ± 7.28 years, 20 males and 26 females, 14 with AD, 18 with VCI and 14 with MD) twice (with interval of 2 years) with the following neuropsychological battery: Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE), Isaac's Set Test (IST for verbal fluency), Literal fluency Test (LFT; variant M-O-H-A in Bulgarian, 1 minute for every letter), Clock Drawing Test (CDT), 10 Words Test (for working memory, delayed recall and recognition (10/20words), Bulgarian variant), Digit Symbol Substitution test (DSST 90sec), Digit Span Test (DST forward and backward) and 21 Hamilton Depression Scale (HDS).

Results: AH itself was not associated with additional cognitive decline. Its role is modified by other factors such as duration of AH, the age of onset of AH, its control and coexistence of more than 4 other vascular risk factors.

Conclusions: The existence of AH itself has no negative effects on cognitive functions. However, its impact on cognition is modified by other important factors such as longer duration and poor control of AH and coexistence of other vascular risk factors.

Keywords: arterial hypertension, Alzheimer's, vascular cognitive impairment, mixed dementia.

The association between arterial hypertension (AH) and cognitive impairment among elderly is complex and disputable (1,4,7). The role of AH on cognitive decline is possibly modified by other important additional factors such as socio-economic factors, gender, race and ethnicity, existence of other comorbidities (diabetes mellitus type 2, obesity, kidney failure, heart failure, etc.) and the age of onset and control of AH (1,3, 4,5,6,7). The exact mechanism of influence of AH on cognitive function is unknown. It is suggested that it causes maladaptation of brain vascular system on abnormal arterial pressure and vascular remodeling (4,7). The high pressure at the distal part of the brain micro-circulation promotes oxidative stress in endothelium cells and increased production of oxygen radicals in mitochondria. AH causes increasing of blood – brain barrier permeability leading to subsequent endothelial impairment, changes of extracellular matrix, damages of pericytes and activation of metal proteases (4,7). The ageing additionally exacerbates AH by inducing micro-vascular and blood-brain barrier damage (7). The blood-brain barrier damage causes neuroinflammation, synapses loss and neurodegeneration. Moreover, AH is associated with accumulation of beta amyloid and increasing of tau phosphorylation (7).

The aim of our study was to examine the association between AH and cognitive decline among elderly patients with Alzheimer's disease (AD), Vascular cognitive impairment (VCI) and mixed (AD and VCI) cognitive impairment (MD).

Material and methods: We examined 100 patients with AH (on average age of 76.72 ± 7.59 years, 28 males and 72 females, 24 with AD, 38 with VCI and 38 with MD) and 46 patients without AH (on average age of 76.67 ± 7.28 years, 20 males and 26 females, 14 with

AD, 18 with VCI and 14 with MD). The inclusion criteria of our study were 1. Age >60 years; 2. Diagnosis of cognitive impairment at the onset of the study confirmed by neuropsychological examination and confirmed diagnosis of AD, VCI or MD on the basis of clinical examination, imaging and laboratory data; 3. Lack of other neurological diseases such as trauma, brain tumors, neuroinfections, demyelinating diseases or epilepsy; 4. Lack of decompensation of coexisted somatic diseases during the study; 5. Lack of psychiatric diseases, except of mild depression or anxiety; 6. Lack of treatment or usage of benzodiazepines, modafinile acetate, hallucinogens and other psychoactive drugs, except for low dosages of Quetiapine (≤ 50 mg/d), Pregabalin (≤ 150 mg/d), Gabaneural (≤ 600 mg/d), Hydroxyzine (≤ 25 mg/d) or antidepressants; 7. Lack of alcohol abuse or usage of forbidden substances; 8. For patients with AH, its duration should be minimum 5 years; 9. Signed informed consent.

After clinical interview and confirmation of diagnosis, the patients were examined via Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE), Isaac's Set Test (IST for verbal fluency), Literal fluency Test (LFT; variant M-O-H-A in Bulgarian, 1 minute for every letter), Clock Drawing Test (CDT), 10 Words Test (for working memory, delayed recall and recognition (10/20words), Bulgarian variant), Digit Symbol Substitution test (DSST 90sec), Digit Span Test (DST forward and backward) and 21 Hamilton Depression Scale (HDS). All patients with HDS above 12 points were excluded.

The patients were examined with the same neuropsychological battery 2 years after the first examination.

The statistical analysis was done via parametric and non-parametric tests as ANOVA, MANOVA, Man-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis test statistics and

simple regression analysis via SPSS 20.0 and Statgraphics 20.0. All results were interpreted at 95% confidential level ($p < 0.05$).

Results:

1. Demographic and clinical data

The demographic data is presented at table 1. Most of our patients were elderly women with additional vascular risk factors (Diabetes mellitus or Insulin resistance, Dyslipidemia, Atrial Fibrillation, Heart failure, Chronic Ischemic Heart Disease, Carotid Atherosclerosis, Kidney Failure or Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease). Among them prevailed the group of patients with VCI, followed by MD and AD. Patients with and without AH had similar demographics and similar additional comorbidities so they could be statistically compared.

The additional data, concerning the characteristics of arterial hypertension is presented at table 2. Most of AH patients had good or moderate control of their blood pressure, although about one fourth of them had poor control. About 1/3 of AH patients had 0 or 1 additional vascular risk factor, 1/3 had 2 to 4 and 1/3 had more than 4 of them.

2. Association between AH and cognitive decline

AH was not associated with additional cognitive decline among all examined patients ($p > 0.05$). Patients with AD and AH had significantly better results on overall cognitive performance, measured by MMSE and slightly better performance on LFT than patients with AD without AH, although there were no differences at other scales (see table 3). Patients with VCI and AH had slightly better results on MMSE than those without AH, but there were no statistical significant differences at other scales. There were no associations between the existence of AH and cognitive functioning on examined scales among patients with MD.

3. The impact of other factors on cognitive performances of patients with AH

3.1 Duration of AH

There was statistically significant association between the duration of AH and cognitive decline – see table 4. Patients with longer AH duration had lower test results on all cognitive scales and moreover they showed severer cognitive decline for 2-year period of the study.

3.2. Early and middle age of onset and late age of onset of AH

Patients with middle and early onset of AH showed lower results on all cognitive scales vs patients with late onset AH (see table 5). Patients with early and middle onset AH showed more severe decline on MMSE, short term verbal memory, recognition (hippocampal memory) and DSST vs those with late onset disease.

3.3. The role of AH control. Patients with good AH control had significantly better results on cognitive scales. They showed mild or no decline during the time of the study (see table 6).

Patients with moderate control showed worse results on MMSE, IST, LFT, short term memory, delayed recall and DSST compared with those with good control. Those differences were relatively small. There

were no differences on cognitive performances between patients with good and moderate control on recognition, CDT and DST.

Patients with poor control had worst results on almost all cognitive scales and they also showed severest decline during the time of the study.

3.4. The role of additional vascular risk factors.

Patients with 0-1 and 2-4 risk factors had similar performances (see table 7). However, those with >4 additional vascular risk factors had poor results on all tests. They also had severest decline on almost all examined scales except for delayed recall and CDT.

Discussion:

AH and dementia frequently coexist in elderly. 68% of our sample had AH, which was most frequent among patients with MD. We failed to find statistically significant differences on cognitive performances of our general sample according to the existence of AH. However, patients with AH showed slightly better MMSE and LFT test performances than those without in AD group, although we failed to find any additional positive effect of AH on cognitive performances on other scales or improvement of any cognitive domain during the period of the study. Patients with VCI and AH also showed better MMSE results vs those without AH, although we also failed to find any additional improvement during the study or associations between AH and examined cognitive functions. So according to our data we might say that the existence of AH hasn't negative effect on cognitive functions of elderly and might eventually has some mild positive effects among patients with AD and VCI. Some other authors also suggest that late onset AH could have some positive effects on cognition in elderly with already developed cognitive impairments and dementia (2,5,10).

The duration of AH is associated with poor cognitive performances at all examined scales and increased cognitive decline among our patients. And although this factor is modified by ageing, it prevails the effect of ageing itself. Zhu et al. (2025) obtained that AH is associated with "more rapid declines in global cognition, orientation, and attention and calculation abilities over time". The duration is also modified by another important factor – the age of onset of AH. We found that patients with AH onset at early and middle life showed significantly lower results and increased decline on all cognitive domains than those with late onset AH. Some authors suggest that middle life hypertension is strongly associated with cognitive impairments and rapid cognitive decline at elderly, but late onset AH shows less impact and even may have some positive effects on cognition (2,5,10). However, according to Zhu and al. (2025) late onset hypertension also leads to accelerated cognitive decline, although not immediately after the onset of AH.

One of the most important modifying factors for the association between AH and cognitive impairment is its control (2,8,10). Patients with good control show significantly better results on all cognitive scales than those with moderate or poor control, having mild (verbal fluency, short term memory and attention) or no additional decline (at overall cognitive performance, recognition and CDT) over the time of the study. Those

with moderate control show slightly poor cognitive performances and more rapid cognitive decline than those with good control. The group of patients with poor control show the worst results and the rapidest decline of almost all cognitive domains. According to us the control of AH is one of the key risk factors for sparing the cognition of elderly with dementia. It can modify the influence of factors such as ageing, age of onset and duration of AH.

The effect of AH on cognition is modified also by the coexistence of other vascular risk factors, that also lead to microvascular brain changes and additional loss of the vascular ability to adapt to high blood pressure (2,5,10). With increasing the number of additional vascular risk factors, we also obtain statistically significant additional cognitive decline at almost all examined cognitive domains, including short term and hippocampal memory and executive functions (working memory, processing speed and attention). Patients with coincidence of middle life onset AH, poor AH control and

vascular risk factors >4 had worst results and rapidest decline even for the short period of follow up (2 years).

Conclusions: AH and cognitive impairments frequently coexist in elderly. The existence of AH itself has no negative effects on cognitive functions. However, its impact on cognition is modified by other important factors such as longer duration and poor control of AH and coexistence of other vascular risk factors.

Limitations of the study: The study was conducted among relatively small sample of patients, followed up for relatively short period of time (2 years).

Informed consent: Each respondent who agreed to participate in the survey signed two copies of an informed consent form; one copy was retained at the Neurology Clinic, where it was saved. For participants who were otherwise vulnerable, informed consent was obtained from a legal guardian.

Table 1.

Demographics and additional vascular risk factors.

	Patients without AH	Patients with AH
N=	46	100
Age (y)	76.67±7.28	76.72±7.59
Sex (Male:Female)	20:26	28:72
Formal education (Basic:Middle:High)	2:30:14	10:53:37
Patients with AD	14	24
Patients with VCI	18	38
Patients with MCI	14	38
Additional vascular risk factors*		
0-1	12	32
2-3	20	32
>4	14	37
Legend: AD – Alzheimer's disease, VCI – vascular cognitive impairment, MCI – mixed cognitive impairment'		
* Additional vascular risk factors – Diabetes mellitus or insulin resistance (confirmed by endocrinologist), Dyslipidemia, Atrial Fibrillation; Heart failure; Chronic Ischemic Heart Disease (confirmed by cardiologist); Carotid atherosclerosis (confirmed by Doppler examination); Kidney failure (confirmed by nephrologist or laboratory data); Chronic Obstructory Pulmonary Disease (confirmed by pulmologist)		

Table 2.

Characteristics of AH

Total number of patients with AH	100
Number of patients with AH development at middle or early ages (<55 y)	47
Number of patients with AH development at late age (>55 y)	54
Duration of AH (y.)	21.90±6.27
Patients with Good control of AH	39
Patients with Moderate control of AH	38
Patients with Poor control of AH	24
Legend: AH – arterial hypertension; Good control – arterial pressure below 140/80mmHg (<130/80 in diabetics), lack of hypertension crises or severe hypotension episodes. Moderate control – arterial pressure at most of the time below 140/80, existence of below 4 crises of hypertension >160/80mmHg or hypotension monthly. Poor control – not fulfill the criteria for good or satisfactory control of blood pressure	

Table 3.

Association between AH and Cognitive functions.

	Overall	AD	VCI	MCI
Patients without AH (1)	46	14	18	14
Patients with AH (2)	100	24	38	38
The association between AH and:				
MMSE 1 (p.)	p>0.05	p=0.0128 Median (1) 20 Median (2) 25	p>0.05	p>0.05
MMSE 2 (p.)	p>0.05	p=0.0133 Median (1) 17.5 Median (2) 23.0	p=0.0428 Median (1) 24 Median (2) 26	p>0.05
Decrease of MMSE (p.)	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05
IST 1 (p.)	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05
IST 2 (p.)	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05
Decrease of IST (p.)	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05
LFT 1 (p.)	p>0.05	p=0.0102 Median (1) 12.5 Median (2) 20	p>0.05	p>0.05
LFT 2 (p.)	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05
Decrease of LFT (p.)	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05
Legend: MMSE – Mini Mental State Examination, IST – Isaac’s Set Test, LFT – Literal Fluency Test 1- at the onset of the study, 2 – at the 2nd year after the onset AD – Alzheimer’s disease VCI – vascular cognitive impairment MCI – Mixed cognitive impairment				

Table 4.

Association between the duration of arterial hypertension and cognitive impairment.

The association between the duration of AH and	Rr	p=
MMSE1 (p.)	-0.71	0.0001
MMSE2 (p.)	-0.79	0.0001
Decline of MMSE (p)	-0.39	0.0001
IST1 (p)	-0.51	0.0001
IST2 (p)	-0.59	0.0001
IST decline (p)	-0.23	0.0200
LFT 1 (p.)	-0.47	0.0001
LFT 2 (p.)	-0.54	0.0001
Decline of LFT (p.)	-0.24	0.0253
10WT – STM 1 (w.)	-0.53	0.0001
10 WT – STM 2 (w.)	-0.64	0.0001
Decline of 10WT-STM (w.)	-0.37	0.0002
10 WT – DR 1 (w.)	-0.42	0.0001
10 WT – DR 2 (w.)	-0.48	0.0001
Decline of 10WT-DR (w.)	-0.42	0.0001
Recognition 1	-0.42	0.0001
Recognition 2	-0.52	0.0001
Decline of recognition	-0.30	0.0025
CDT 1 (errors)	0.42	0.0001
CDT 2 (errors)	0.55	0.0001
Increasing of errors on CDT	0.21	0.0424
DST forward 1 (p.)	-0.45	0.0001
DST forward 2 (p.)	-0.56	0.0001
Decline of DST forward	-0.27	0.0098
DST backward 1 (p.)	-0.41	0.0001
DST backward 2 (p.)	-0.61	0.0001
Decline of DST backward	-0.26	0.0110
DSST 1 (p.)	-0.58	0.0001
DSST 2 (p.)	-0.70	0.0001
Decline of DSST	-0.47	0.0001

Legend: rr – coefficient of correlation; MMSE – Mini Mental State Examination; IST Isaac's Set Test; LFT – literal fluency test; 10 WT – STM – the average result of 5 trials for immediate response on 10 words test; 10 WT – DR – the 5 min delayed recall on 10WT; CDT – Clock Drawing Test; DST – Digit Span Test; DSST – Digit Symbol substitution test; AH – arterial hypertension

Table 5.

The association between early/middle onset and late onset AH on cognitive performance.

	Early and middle AH onset (average)	Late onset AH (average)	p=
MMSE1 (p.)	21.38	26.87	0.0001
MMSE2 (p.)	18.85	26.48	0.0001
Decline of MMSE (p)	-2.49	-0.45	0.0005
IST1 (p)	25.65	33.37	0.0001
IST2 (p)	23.17	32.46	0.0001
IST decline (p)	NA	NA	>0.05
LFT 1 (p.)	19.95	25.81	0.0025
LFT 2 (p.)	15.35	23.19	0.0003
Decline of LFT (p.)	NA	NA	>0.05
10WT – STM 1 (w.)	4.37	5.61	0.0001
10 WT – STM 2 (w.)	3.67	5.31	0.0001
Decline of 10WT-STM (w.)	-0.68	-0.32	0.0172
10 WT – DR 1 (w.)	2.16	3.91	0.0001
10 WT – DR 2 (w.)	1.28	3.43	0.0001
Decline of 10WT-DR (w.)	NA	NA	p>0.05
Recognition 1	16.04	17.40	0.0030
Recognition 2	13.96	16.85	0.0001
Decline of recognition	-2.04	-0.62	0.0018
CDT 1 (errors)	2.26	0.86	0.0007
CDT 2 (errors)	2.87	1.10	0.0001
Increasing of errors on CDT	NA	NA	p>0.05
DST forward 1 (p.)	5.70	6.33	0.0256
DST forward 2 (p.)	4.93	5.90	0.0030
Decline of DST forward	NA	NA	p>0.05
DST backward 1 (p.)	2.23	3.98	0.0158
DST backward 2 (p.)	2.288	3.51	0.0001
Decline of DST backward	NA	NA	p>0.05
DSST 1 (p.)	21.90	32.66	0.0001
DSST 2 (p.)	16.25	30.31	0.0001
Decline of DSST	-4.95	-1.96	0.0048

Legend: MMSE – Mini Mental State Examination; IST Isaac's Set Test; LFT – literal fluency test; 10 WT – STM – the average result of 5 trials for immediate response on 10 words test; 10 WT – DR – the 5 min delayed recall on 10WT; CDT – Clock Drawing Test; DST – Digit Span Test; DSST – Digit Symbol substitution test; AH – arterial hypertension

The role of AH control on cognitive performances.

	Good control of blood pressure (Median)	Moderate control of blood pressure (Median)	Poor control of blood pressure (Median)	P
MMSE1 (p.)	27	25	19	0.0001
MMSE2 (p.)	28	23	15	0.0001
Decline of MMSE (p)	0	-1	-3.5	0.0001
IST1 (p)	34	32	24	0.0002
IST2 (p)	34	29	19	0.0001
IST decline (p)	-1	-2	-3	0.0226
LFT 1 (p.)	24	25	17	0.0392
LFT 2 (p.)	21	20	12	0.0011
Decline of LFT (p.)	-1	-2	-6	0.0287
10WT – STM 1 (w.)	5.6	5	4.2	0.0003
10 WT – STM 2 (w.)	5.5	4	3	0.0001
Decline of 10WT-STM (w.)	-0.2	-0.2	-0.6	0.0003
10 WT – DR 1 (w.)	4	3	2	0.0034
10 WT – DR 2 (w.)	4	2	0	0.0001
Decline of 10WT-DR (w.)	0	-1	0	0.0180
Recognition 1	17	17	16	0.0297
Recognition 2	17	16	12	0.0001
Decline of recognition	0	0	-2	0.0005
CDT 1 (errors)	0	0	3	0.0021
CDT 2 (errors)	0	1	4	0.0001
Increasing of errors on CDT	NA	NA	NA	p>0.05
DST forward 1 (p.)	NA	NA	NA	p>0.05
DST forward 2 (p.)	6	6	4	0.0007
Decline of DST forward	0	0	-1	0.0340
DST backward 1 (p.)	4	4	3	0.0336
DST backward 2 (p.)	3	3	2	0.0001
Decline of DST backward	0	0	-2	0.0084
DSST 1 (p.)	31	31.5	17	0.0043
DSST 2 (p.)	31	25	10	0.0001
Decline of DSST	-1.5	3	7	0.0009

Legend: MMSE – Mini Mental State Examination; IST Isaac's Set Test; LFT – literal fluency test; 10 WT – STM – the average result of 5 trials for immediate response on 10 words test; 10 WT – DR – the 5 min delayed recall on 10WT; CDT – Clock Drawing Test; DST – Digit Span Test; DSST – Digit Symbol substitution test; AH – arterial hypertension

The role of additional risk factors on cognition.

	Patients with 0 or 1 additional risk factors (median)	Patients with 2-4 additional risk factors (median)	Patients with >4 additional risk factors (median)	P
MMSE1 (p.)	28	26	21	0.0001
MMSE2 (p.)	28	25	18	0.0001
Decline of MMSE (p)	0	-0.5	3.0	0.0001
IST1 (p)	36	32	24	0.0001
IST2 (p)	36	30	21	0.0001
IST decline (p)	-1	-1	-3	0.0057
LFT 1 (p.)	25	26	17	0.0024
LFT 2 (p.)	21	24	12	0.0001
Decline of LFT (p.)	-1	-1	-6	0.0042
10WT – STM 1 (w.)	5.6	5	4.1	0.0001
10 WT – STM 2 (w.)	5.6	4.8	3.0	0.0001
Decline of 10WT-STM (w.)	-0.2	-0.2	-0.8	0.0001
10 WT – DR 1 (w.)	5	3	2	0.0001
10 WT – DR 2 (w.)	4	2	0	0.0001
Decline of 10WT-DR (w.)	NA	NA	NA	p>0.05
Recognition 1	18	17	16	0.0079
Recognition 2	17	17	14	0.0001
Decline of recognition	0	0	-2	0.0002
CDT 1 (errors)	0	0	1	0.0092
CDT 2 (errors)	0	1	4	0.0001
Increasing of errors on CDT	NA	NA	NA	p>0.05
DST forward 1 (p.)	6	6	5	0.0094
DST forward 2 (p.)	6	6	4	0.0001
Decline of DST forward	0	0	-1	0.0002
DST backward 1 (p.)	4	4	3	0.0096
DST backward 2 (p.)	3.5	3	2	0.0001
Decline of DST backward	0	0	-1	0.0054
DSST 1 (p.)	38	31	18	0.0001
DSST 2 (p.)	36	25	10	0.0001
Decline of DSST	-1	-2.5	-6.5	0.0001

Legend: MMSE – Mini Mental State Examination; IST Isaac's Set Test; LFT – literal fluency test; 10 WT – STM – the average result of 5 trials for immediate response on 10 words test; 10 WT – DR – the 5 min delayed recall on 10WT; CDT – Clock Drawing Test; DST – Digit Span Test; DSST – Digit Symbol substitution test; AH – arterial hypertension

References

1. Canavan M, O'Donnell MJ. Hypertension and Cognitive Impairment: A Review of Mechanisms and Key Concepts. *Front Neurol.* 2022 Feb 4;13:821135.
2. Castilla-Guerra L. Late-life hypertension as a risk factor for cognitive decline and dementia. *Hypertens Res.* 2022 Oct;45(10):1670-1671.
3. Iadecola C, Gottesman RF. Neurovascular and Cognitive Dysfunction in Hypertension. *Circ Res.* 2019 Mar 29;124(7):1025-1044.
4. Levine DA, Springer MV, Brodtmann A. Blood Pressure and Vascular Cognitive Impairment. *Stroke.* 2022 Apr;53(4):1104-1113.
5. Sánchez-Nieto JM, Rivera-Sánchez UD, Mendoza-Núñez VM. Relationship between Arterial Hypertension with Cognitive Performance in Elderly. *Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.* *Brain Sci.* 2021 Oct 29;11(11):1445.
6. Santos CY, Snyder PJ, Wu WC, Zhang M, Echeverria A, Alber J. Pathophysiologic relationship between Alzheimer's disease, cerebrovascular disease,

and cardiovascular risk: A review and synthesis. *Alzheimers Dement (Amst).* 2017 Feb 9;7:69-87.

7. Ungvari Z, Toth P, Tarantini S, Prodan CI, Sorond F, Merkely B, Csiszar A. Hypertension-induced cognitive impairment: from pathophysiology to public health. *Nat Rev Nephrol.* 2021 Oct;17(10):639-654.

8. Yan X, Meng T, Liu H, Liu J, Du J, Chang C. The Association Between the Duration, Treatment, Control of Hypertension and Lifestyle Risk Factors in Middle-Aged and Elderly Patients with Mild Cognitive Impairment: A Case-Control Study. *Neuropsychiatr Dis Treat.* 2022 Mar 19;18:585-595.

9. Zhu S, Bo J, Xia T, Gu X. Temporal patterns of cognitive decline after hypertension onset among middle-aged and older adults in China. *Sci Rep.* 2025 May 10;15(1):16300.

10. Zúñiga Salazar G, Zúñiga D, Balasubramanian S, Mehmood KT, Al-Baldawi S. The Relation Between Arterial Hypertension and Cognitive Impairment: A Literature Review. *Cureus.* 2024 Jan 23;16(1):e52782.